

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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INCORPORATION OF BIO-CERAMIC ENDODONTIC SEALERS INTO DENTAL PRACTICE**Kudrat-Zoda K.A.**

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Resume. Dental materials research is taking a new turn with bioceramic endodontic sealers. Their outstanding mechanical and physical characteristics portend a bright future for them as materials for root canal obturation, particularly in the management of apical disease. The paper discusses clinical instances of bioceramic sealers being successfully used to treat apical periodontitis and provides a comprehensive evaluation of bioceramic endodontic sealers.

Keywords: root canal obturation, endodontic therapy, sealer, bioceramics, and apical periodontitis.

БИОКЕРАМИК ЭНДОДОНТИК СИЛЕРЛАРНИ СТОМАТОЛОГИК АМАЛИЁТГА ЖОРИЙ ЭТИШ**Кудрат-Зода К.А.**

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Резюме. Стоматологик материаллар бўйича тадқиқотлар биокерамик эндодонтик силерлар билан янги босқичга чиқмоқда. Уларнинг ажойиб механик ва физикавий хусусиятлари уларга илдиз каналларини обтурация қилиш учун, айниқса апикал касалликларни бошқаришда, катта келажакни башорат қилмоқда. Ушбу мақолада апикал периодонтитни даволашда биокерамик силерлардан муваффақиятли фойдаланишнинг клиник ҳолатлари муҳокама қилинади ва биокерамик эндодонтик силерларнинг ҳар томонлама баҳоси берилади.

Калит сўзлар: илдиз канали обтурацияси, эндодонтик даволаш, силер, биокерамика, апикал периодонтит.

ВНЕДРЕНИЕ БИОКЕРАМИЧЕСКИХ ЭНДОДОНТИЧЕСКИХ СИЛЕРОВ В СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКУЮ ПРАКТИКУ**Кудрат-Зода К.А.**

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Резюме. Исследования стоматологических материалов выходят на новый виток с появлением биокерамических эндодонтических силеров. Их выдающиеся механические и физические характеристики предвещают им большое будущее в качестве материалов для обтурации корневых каналов, особенно в лечении апикальных заболеваний. В статье обсуждаются клинические случаи успешного использования биокерамических силеров для лечения апикального периодонтита и представлена всесторонняя оценка биокерамических эндодонтических силеров.

Ключевые слова: обтурация корневого канала, эндодонтическое лечение, силер, биокерамика, апикальный периодонтит.

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Introduction: Innovative methods, strategies, and tools are continuously being brought into the area of dentistry as a result of major advances in science and technology. Specialists are becoming more qualified, and the success rate of the medical treatment they deliver is rising in tandem. Endodontics has a unique niche in the dental sector. Endodontists operate with the root canal system, which has an infinitely complicated internal structure. The precision and skill of the activities performed at each step of root canal therapy are critical to the success of endodontic treatment. Here, the initial diagnosis, the following appropriate repair of the tooth's crown, and the intricacy of the canal architecture all play important roles. The last step in endodontic therapy is obturation of the root canal system space. The goal of this procedure is to shield the treated root canal system against infection, either primary or secondary. It promotes the recovery of periodontal tissues or keeps them in a healthy condition, and it has a respectable degree of biocompatibility [1, 5]. There are many different needs for sealing materials, and they change based on practical duties as well as biological and physical properties. The dental industry now offers a large variety of endodontic sealers, including preparations based on zinc oxide and eugenol, glass ionomer cements, materials based on epoxy resin, and mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA) [1, 2, 6]. Bio-ceramic endodontic sealers, a kind of hygroscopic dental

materials (HDM), represent a new frontier in dental materials research. A hygroscopic inorganic chemical (or compounds) such as calcium silicates, calcium aluminates, zinc sulfate, or calcium sulfate reacting with water (hydration reaction) forms the basis for the majority of the curing process. They may be offered in a pre-mixed form that interacts with the tissue (dental) fluid in situ, or as a powder that has to be combined with water before use. The high alkalinity of this class of materials is caused by the precipitated calcium forming calcium hydroxide. The material undergoes biological integration through the formation of hydroxyapatite when calcium ions interact with phosphate ions found in bodily tissues [2–4, 6, 10, 13, 16]. All generations of bioceramic materials may be categorized into four major classes depending on the primary active component: experimental calcium aluminosilicates, calcium silicate-based, calcium phosphate-based (hydroxyapatite (HA)), and a combination of calcium silicate and calcium phosphate (HA).

GCM group materials may be offered as a cement composition or as a paste and sealant that are then mixed with a main solid carrier. Pre-mixing is necessary for bioceramic endodontic sealers, which may be a powder-liquid system. It should be mentioned that the handling and physical characteristics of the material may be impacted by this technique's high sensitivity. On the other hand, the product may be offered already blended. In this instance, the fluids around the living tissue will be involved in the curing process [2, 8–13]. Bioceramic endodontic sealers' attributes include: • high pH values (up to 12.5);

- excellent sealing;
- ability to form a chemical bond with the tooth structure;
- lack of mutagenic activity and low cytotoxicity;
- ability to harden and gain strength in a moist environment;
- lack of shrinkage phenomena during material hardening;
- internal osteoinductivity because they can absorb osteoinductive substances if a bone healing process is taking place nearby;
- antibacterial properties;
- good radiopacity [2, 7, 8, 13, 16].

Mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA) is the first generation of bioceramic materials. Portland cement is regarded as its creator (PC). At one point, it was only used in the building sector. A novel substance called MTA was produced by adding a radiopaque filler (bismuth oxide) and changing the chemical makeup of PC. It was the most well-known hygroscopic dental material for a long period. Nonetheless, the technology for MTA-based root canal obturation materials is still evolving. In particular, many businesses have begun producing new MTA generations, which has resulted in a more or less significant alteration to the MTA's chemical structure, including the radiopaque filler. The dental materials industry now offers a large range of GIC products [2, 4, 11, 12, 14]. "Dia-Root" ("Dia Dent") and "Sure-Seal Root" ("Sure Dent") are the two materials from the bioceramic endodontic sealers group that are currently approved in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Investigating the efficacy of materials from the bioceramic endodontic sealers group in the management of persistent apical disease is the study's goal.

Materials and Methods: We used the bioceramic endodontic sealer "Sure-Seal Root" ("Sure Dent") to conduct endodontic treatment for clinical studies of a novel class of materials. In order to withdraw the root canal of tooth 1.3 for future prostheses, patient R. sought advice from a prosthodontist. According to the patient's medical history, the tooth had previously undergone treatment for complex caries.

Clinical picture: percussion is faintly positive, tooth 1.3 is discolored, has a carious cavity on its surface, and has an unsatisfactory filling on its palatal and proximal surfaces. The mucosal transition fold around the 1.3 tooth root projection showed no alterations. On the radiograph, a distinct bone deterioration lesion spanning 5.16 x 2.43 cm is seen in the apical region, the obturation is not thick, and the root canal of tooth 1.3 is filled to ½ of its length. The PAI index was determined to be 4 after evaluating the endodontic condition and the radiographic imaging of inflammation. This tooth's COPI index code, according to the PEES scale, is S3R1D1, and its ETTI index is L2H2CS2CF5 [16]. Our own study has led us to create a logically constructed and user-friendly periapical index, which will be included in further publications. The diagnosis is tooth 1.3's chronic apical periodontitis. Together with the patient, the following treatment plan was decided upon and put into action. Carious tissue and the failing restoration are removed, and the tooth is isolated using a rubber dam device. removing the root canal's seal, using an apex finder to measure its working length, and controlling radiography. E3 Azure rotary instruments (EndoStar Poldent) were used for the root canal procedure (final file 35/04), along with EDTA (17%) and sodium hypochlorite (3%) as medicine. solutions that are activated for 30 to 60 seconds using an endoactivator. Using the cold hydraulic condensation method and the bioceramic sealer "Sure-Seal Root" ("Sure Dent"), root canal obturation is accomplished using tapered gutta-percha. In a really conservative approach to endodontic treatment, this conceptual approach permits the use of rotating tools (producing a continuous taper of 0.04 or 0.06). The steps are as follows:

Squeeze a tiny amount of material into the root canal slowly; remove the syringe tip and apply a thin layer of material to the master cone; insert the master cone into the root canal to its full working length; remove any extra gutta-percha material. The syringe tip should be inserted into the canal no deeper than the coronal third. Glass ionomer cement is used to seal the tooth's crown, delaying prostheses. dynamic monitoring at three, six, and twelve months. After a year, a follow-up examination revealed no alterations in the mucosa in tooth 1.3's projection, no complaints, and a sealed repair with painless percussion. The radiograph shows that the root canal is firmly obturated over its whole length, and the apical region shows evidence of bone tissue healing together with a modest enlargement of the periodontal space. The COPI and ETTI are S0R0D0 and L1H1CS1CF0, respectively, while the PAI index is equal to 2.

Conclusion: The capacity to harden in a wet environment and the potential to have a reparative and osteogenic impact are two of the many advantageous qualities of bioceramic endodontic sealers, a new generation of obturation materials. Positive dynamics in the reparative processes were shown as a consequence of dynamic surveillance of a clinical instance of apical periodontitis treatment employing a bioceramic endodontic sealer, indicating their great efficiency.

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